

POLICY BRIEF: THE BENEFICIARIES OF NEW YORK CITY'S 421-A TAX EXEMPTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This Policy Brief provides evidence which supports the pending 421-a legislative proposal of the Mayor's Office of the City of New York supported by the Real Estate Board of New York. Specifically, this Policy Brief provides evidence that condominium subsidies—and their end-user beneficiaries—are no longer consistent with the public policies of promoting the affordability of housing. Evidence is provided which demonstrates that the city would save hundreds of millions of dollars a year if the condominium subsidies were dropped pursuant to the pending reform. Likewise, evidence is provided which suggests that an outright repeal of 421-a could be disruptive to affordable housing developments that must rely on a variety of subsidizes to bridge the affordability gap. Finally, it is argued that by focusing exclusively on rental housing, 421-a has the potential to leverage greater amounts of affordable housing across all five boroughs.

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I. INTRODUCTION

This Policy Brief (this “Brief”) helps partially answer the question as to who really benefits from 421-a. The research provides an empirical basis for supporting the pending legislative proposal of the Mayor of the City of New York (Mayor’s Office) which is supported by the Real Estate Board of New York (REBNY). This research highlights the disproportionate benefit gained from condominium development which is no longer consistent with either the Mayor’s or the Governor’s public policy goals. However, it also highlights the extent to which affordable housing has been produced under the program and the extent to which there is capacity for future development utilizing the subsidy. While not definitive in its analysis, as the exogeneity of the city’s real estate markets defies precise scientific testing, most economists polled on the issue agree that the subsidy has already been priced into the land price and is offering marginal benefits to certain markets and demographics. However, the slim margins for affordable housing—together with declining federal subsidies—dictate that the current deal being put forth before the state legislature has the potential to fundamentally support the provision of affordable housing in a manner which is economically on par with other production subsidies. However, it is not just about affordable housing. The city also has the responsibility to promote vast amounts of market rate rental housing to support middle-income households who are also feeling the pressure of a lack of a lack of relative affordability. It is anticipated that this Brief will help inform the current policy debate, as the outcome of the debate will have tremendous impacts on the housing of millions of New Yorkers.

One of the foremost challenges facing New York City is the lack of affordable housing. However, it was not that long ago that the city faced a similar crisis driven by too few people. The 421-a Partial Tax Exemption for New Multiple Dwellings (hereinafter referred to as “421-a”) is a 44-year old tax incentive that has subsidized most of New York City’s multi-family residential construction since it first began in 1971. At the time, it was created to stimulate housing development in an era when the city was plagued by residential disinvestment and population flight to the suburbs. As real estate investment grew through the years, the program has met growing criticism and implemented a series of reforms that would justify the exemption by modifying it to include affordable housing provisions. Despite reforms, 421-a remains a program that primarily subsidizes market-rate development. The relevance of 421-a and its efficacy in providing affordable housing are being questioned as it approaches its expiration date on June 15, and the program has become the subject of great controversy.

FIGURE 1: New York City’s Tax Expenditure by Category and Program

\$7,237 million estimated total expenditure
Data from the Office of Tax Policy’s Annual report on tax expenditures: Fiscal Year 2015

In recent years, the 421-a exemption has been the single largest tax expenditure program in New York City (Office of Tax Policy, 2015; Wu, 2012). For the 2015 fiscal year, the program totaled over \$1.1 billion, and formed 15% of all tax expenditures for the city. The 421-a exemption expenditure is over 60% more than the second most expensive program, the Industrial & Commercial Incentive Program at \$685.8 million, and is more than twice the amount of the third highest expenditure, the New York City Housing Authority (Office of Tax Policy, 2015).

Full program benefits are granted for up to 3 years during the construction period for all 421-a properties. The benefit start year begins after construction is complete, and the length of the exemption granted depends on location and project type; all exemption lengths include a number of years with full benefits, followed by a phase-out period that lasts until the exemption term is over (NYC Housing Preservation & Development, n.d.). Many rental units built under the program, whether they are affordable or market-rate, are subject to rent stabilization for the duration of the benefits, where the initial rents are set by the Tax Incentive Programs (NYC Housing Preservation & Development (HPD), n.d.). However, the market effectively sets the rents, as allowable maximum rents set by HPD rarely constrain what the building owner would get in the market. There are no such limitations for condominium properties.

The most outspoken parties in favor of renewing 421-a in its entirety have been property developers, who argue that the cost of construction, together with unprecedented inflationary land pricing pressures from global capital have resulted in a distorted market which needs subsidies to keep rents and sales prices from reflecting these historically unprecedented inflows of capital (Hutchins, 2015; Observer.com Editors, 2015). However, critics claim that 421-a is allowing tax dollars to subsidize luxury housing and the wealthy elite, while the small affordable housing component does not justify the cost of the program (Hutchins, 2015). The Association for Neighborhood & Housing Development (ANHD) estimated that less than 9 percent of the units developed under the program qualified as affordable housing. Additionally, 421-a is often used with the Inclusionary Housing Program (IHP) and other low income tax bonds and credits, which has allowed developers to double or triple-dip in affordable housing incentives by using the same 20% of affordable units to realize benefits under multiple programs, (Association for Neighborhood and Housing Development, 2014, 2015; Brewer, 2015).

This Brief attempts to investigate the outstanding hypothesis that 421-a's shortcomings have been its disproportionate benefits to those who are not necessarily the intended beneficiaries of the program from the perspective of current policy priorities. However, the secondary intent is to demonstrate where and to what extent 421-a is or has historically supported the provision of affordable rental housing. This Brief will begin with an evaluation of the current distribution of subsidy recipients in order to determine who is receiving the benefit at a broader scale, and will then further focus on the effect of the tax exemption on recent condominium sales in two neighborhoods with distinctly different characteristics: Manhattan's Upper West Side between 59th and 79th Streets and Morrisania/Longwood in the Bronx. It is anticipated that the research will provide greater insight into the complexity of the role of 421-a and its impact on housing production.

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

Methodology

The research was initiated with a review of existing literature, followed by data mining and analysis whose results tempered further investigation through neighborhood level case studies. While much of the rhetorical and political critiques targeted against the 421-a program were focused on luxury condominiums, there were few studies that dealt with the program as applied to condominiums specifically. As such, data analysis was undertaken at the city level and those findings were utilized to perform regression analysis on the sale of properties collecting 421-a exemptions so as to better understand how the exemption has impacted condominium sales.

City-wide Data Gathering, Cleanup, and Analysis

The initial data sets were populated by the generation of comprehensive lists of properties receiving 421-a by borough from the Department of Finance (DOF) website. Additionally, this data was augmented by information compiled by the Independent Budget Office (IBO) with the help of the Municipal Art Society (MAS), detailing 2013-2014 fiscal year information for 421-a exempt properties and the amount of subsidy collected. Unlike most of the other data, this data set was aggregated to the level of the building, not individual condominium units. Another set of data, compiled by DOF in February of 2015 was obtained which included base year assessed values and updated numbers for the 2014-2015 fiscal year. However, these numbers did not include benefit amounts.

Estimates of construction discounts for each property were calculated from this compiled data, based on the assessed value in year 1 of the exemption. It was assumed that assessed values rose by 4% each year, an increase commonly used by assessors, and that the assessed value rose consistently in the three years from the construction start date to the benefit start date. The estimated construction discount was calculated as follows, where “AV” stands for “assessed value.”

$$\text{Construction Discount} = [(AV_{Year1} - AV_{Base}) \times (.75 + .5 + .25)] \times TaxRate$$

Most of the background research involved merging information from multiple datasets together, usually through borough-block-lot identifiers (BBLs). For instances where building level data had to be matched against individual condo level data, a combination of “borough-block-condo identifier” or “borough-block-address number” was used in order to join parent condominium BBL identifiers to their parent lot numbers. Neither method produced perfect match percentages; but, together these data sets were able to match all but 263 out of the 9,209 buildings represented against the DOF individual property data. The final MAS combined data also included slightly more units than the DOF online data, a total of 153,091 rather than 153,290 residential units.

TABLE 1: *Data Sources for Background Research*

Source	Data type	Data set/tool	Time period / version	Scale
421-a general information				
DOF	Table	Comprehensive properties currently receiving 421-a	All current exemptions	Individual property
DOF	Table	Comprehensive properties currently receiving 421-a. Does not include expenditure, but includes base values.	All exemptions (Fiscal year 2014-2015), compiled February 2015	Individual property
MAS/IBO	Table	421-a general information. Includes exemption expenditure.	All exemptions (Fiscal year 2013-2014)	Building (condos aggregated)
HPD	Table	Borough-block-lot numbers within GEA	New Geographic Exclusion Area (GEA) beginning July 1, 2008	Individual property
Mapping				
DCP	Geographic	MapPLUTO	2014v1	Building tax lot (parent of individual property lot)
DOF	Geographic	Tax Blocks	August 2014	Building tax block

The map of the Geographic Exclusion Area (GEA) and the DOF neighborhoods were both created by taking the borough-block portion of the databases from the Housing Preservation Department (HPD) and DOF, and matching them against borough-block numbers in the DOF tax block map. For both data sets, it was assumed that the definition of zones included entire blocks. To determine whether a unit was within or outside of the GEA, it was mapped in ArcGIS by borough-block identifier. The current GEA list by HPD was missing borough-block identifiers within the original GEA of central Manhattan, and this area was added by hand. In mapping DOF neighborhoods, the centroid of all blocks included in each neighborhood in the data was used as a point representation. The output was inaccurate for neighborhood locations in the Bronx, Queens, and Staten Island, and was manually modified based on references from the New York City Neighborhood Tabulation Areas GIS file and Google Maps.

Neighborhood Case Study Data Collection and Processing

The premium realized on sale prices by 421-a subsidy was analyzed by looking at the price per square foot of housing as a function of the following variables:

- Year built
- Year purchased
- Number of bedrooms
- Estimated 421-a tax discount remaining at time of sale

Not all datasets had complete information, and a sale observation was only considered usable if all of the above data was available for the property and sale. Only sales of current 421-a properties were included in the research. The DOF sales data included the time periods from January of 2003 until November of 2014 and included a neighborhood definition for each line item. The following filters were applied:

- Neighborhood: Manhattan’s Upper West Side between 59th and 79th Streets, and Morrisania/Longwood in the Bronx.
- Price: Eliminated sales prices of \$0.
- Building class categories: Residential only
- Residential units: Records with 1 residential unit transacted only
- Commercial units: Records with 0 commercial units transacted only

A simplified version of the data was processed using inflation data from the Bureau of Labor Statistics and saved, containing the following fields:

- Borough-Block-Lot code
- Original sale amount
- Sale date
- Original sale year
- Sale amount in 2015 dollars
- Neighborhood

The following additional fields were added based on whether a property’s borough-block-identifier was found in the DOF list of 421-a properties:

- Is on 421-a list
- Base year of benefit
- Benefit start year
- Benefit length
- Base year assessed value
- Effective assessed value

The DOF 421-a and sales data sets were missing many of the variables needed for analysis. These variable data sets were obtained using Python web scraping scripts which submitted individual borough-block-lot identifiers to the DOF NYC Property Portal, the Department of Finance, NYC Property lookup and Property Shark websites.

TABLE 2: *Additional Data Sources for Neighborhood Regression Case Studies*

Source	Data type	Data set/tool	Time period / version	Scale
Property sales				
DOF	Table	Annualized and rolling sales data	January 2003-November 2014	Individual property
Additional property databases queried for regression				
DOF	Individual record	Property portal: Tax benefit search	Filtered records from DOF sales: Buildings built after 1960	Individual property
DOF	Individual record	NYC Property search: most recent tax bill	Filtered records from DOF sales: Buildings built after 1960	Individual property
Property Shark	Individual record	Public property search	Filtered records from DOF sales: Buildings built after 1960	Individual property

The following diagram shows the final results of aggregation for the condominium sales analysis and where each piece of information was extracted from and in what order of validation.

FIGURE 2: Diagram of Data Collection Process for Neighborhood Case Studies

Existing dataset	Variable key	Notes
Scraped dataset	Final regression: Independent variable Dependent variable	*Data existed in multiple sources, but most complete/standardized format from this source **Multiple data sources combined for most complete information
Processed dataset	Used in non-regression charts/visualizations	

Additional information had to be calculated from data pulled from the previously cited sources. Primarily, in order to understand the costs, all monetary values were converted to 2015 dollars using the inflation table in the Appendix, accessed from the Bureau of Labor Statistics. In order to calculate the estimated cumulative exemption benefits left for a property at the time of each sale, the current exemption amount was cross-referenced against the year of exemption at time of sale and phase-out plans for each exemption length, using the tables found on the DOF's website (see Appendix). From here, the phase-out value for each year was determined and summed in order to find the cumulative exemption left at time of sale. Property information may or may not have had an available tax bill. For properties without a tax bill available but with effective assessed values and base values available for a given year, a tax rate of 12.855% was used to calculate out both past and future exemptions. Using the following calculation, where "AV" stands for "Assessed Value," all missing variables in the equation could be found under either circumstance.

$$Exemption_{Current} = (AV_{Current} - AV_{BaseYear}) \times TaxRate \times PhaseOutPercentage_{Current}$$

For both properties with available tax bills and without, this method uses the same tax rate for each year of calculation. This compensates for past higher tax rates, and assumes lower rates in the future. A steady tax percentage for the calculations was used in order to balance out the two discrepancies in the absence of knowledge of future property tax rates. As previously referenced, an assessed value rise of 4% per year was factored in.

$$AV_{CurrentYear} = AV_{PastYear} \times 1.04$$

Exemption discounts for each year were calculated based on the assessed value, phase-out percentage for that year, and tax rate from the current year. However, construction benefits were not included for the regression study.

$$TotalExemption_{YearOfSale} = \sum_{YearOfSale}^{YearExpires} (AV_{Year} - AV_{BaseYear}) \times TaxRate \times PhaseOutPercentage_{Year}$$

Sales were only considered usable if all of the variables for regression were available. Any sale price with a price per square foot of less than \$100 or more than \$15,000 were discarded from the sample. All data tables included in the regression results display monetary value in 2015 dollars.

A natural log transformation was applied to both price per square foot and the cumulative exemption left at time of sale, in order to adjust the logarithmic growth of numbers to fit a linear regression model. The final regression equation would be expressed as:

$$\ln(PricePerSqFt) = Coef_{.1} * SaleYr + Coef_{.2} * YearBuilt + Coef_{.3} * \ln(ExemptionLeftPerSqFt) + Constant$$

There are some factors that this model may not account for, such as whether a building has an elevator, is near a subway or the homeowner's workplace, or the effect of other financial incentives or disincentives such as transfer taxes (Kopczuk & Munroe, 2013).

III. BACKGROUND RESEARCH

History of Reform

The 421-a program began in 1971 to encourage new market-rate residential construction. It was based on a similar program from 1920, which used tax incentives to reduce housing shortages in New York City after World War I (Konopko, 1986). It first came under public scrutiny in 1984 when then Mayor Ed Koch attempted to deny the \$50 million benefit to the Trump Tower on Fifth Avenue and was ultimately forced to do so when Donald Trump brought the case as a lawsuit in state court (MAS, 2015). Shortly afterward, a Geographic Exclusion Area (GEA) was formed for the first time, spanning roughly the area between 14th Street and 96th Street in Manhattan, within which properties could only qualify for the program if they provided affordable housing (MAS, 2015). Although, the real impetus was not so much Trump as it was the desire to overcome a previous provision which required sites to be underutilized or obsolete. Along with the creation of the GEA in the 1980's, a negotiable certificate program was formulated, which offered affordable housing developments to receive four to six certificates for each affordable unit constructed, which were then sold to developers within the GEA (Wu, 2012).

FIGURE 3: Current Geographic Exclusion Area for the Program

An additional round of reform took place between 2006 and 2008. Among them, the GEA was expanded to its current limits, which include all of Manhattan and certain parts of the outer boroughs (Chase, 2007; Wambua, 2013). For properties within the GEA, affordable housing was required to be developed on-site. With this new wave for reform, the negotiable certificate program was phased-out. Additionally, 35-year affordability and rent stabilization requirements were put into place, so that all affordable units must remain rent-stabilized for 35 years after construction completion (Wambua, 2013). A cap on the exemption was created for as-of-right market-rate apartments outside of the GEA, originally set for the first \$65,000 of assessed property value and increasing every year thereafter by 3%. When a unit is subject to the exemption cap, any additional assessed value after the cap limit is not eligible for exemption benefits. This was intended to make sure there is a limit to the amount of exemption provided for market-rate housing built under the program. The effect of the exemption cap is shown in the equation below, where “AV” stands for “assessed value.”

$$\text{Capped exemption discount} = [\text{Min}(AV_{\text{CurrentYear}}, AV_{\text{ExemptionCap}}) - AV_{\text{BaseYear}}] \times \text{TaxRate}$$

421-a as Public Policy

From a public policy perspective, the goals of 421-a can be debated as an incentive for developers to build housing for both market-rate and affordable housing or a means to promote the production of affordable housing. The primary target of affordable housing regulation is often supply-side incentives and regulation, as it has historically been more efficient for cities to engage housing economics on the supply side of the equation. Both the Bloomberg and de Blasio administrations have placed heavy emphasis on addressing affordable housing through supply-side subsidies (Mayor’s Office of the City of New York, 2004; Mayor’s Office of the City of New York, 2014). This was primarily done through developer subsidies during the Bloomberg administration, and Mayor de Blasio has stated that 421-a program is still a critical tool for meeting his goal of providing 80,000 more affordable housing units in the next ten years (Real Estate Board of New York, 2015).

In New York City, especially Manhattan, land pricing is the principle constraint on the development of affordable housing. Developers commonly cite land prices as the major hurdle to being able to build anything other than high-end residential buildings. Regulatory measures often aim to ease the burden of construction and land costs—a huge portion of supply-side decisions (Adams & Füss, 2010; Kenny, 1999). If 421-a is not renewed, the first speculated market effect is a drop in land values in select areas. However, this theory is largely untested. Although, impossibly high land prices are often the cited culprit for difficulties in building affordable housing in the city, REBNY also argues that falling land prices as a reaction to the disappearance of the 421-a program could cause further barriers to affordable housing development by creating a “development freeze,” which would run counter to supply-side affordable housing efforts (Hutchins, 2015).

In addition to the general debate about tax exemptions and their effects on generating residential construction, the exemption as applied to different types of housing units can be captured in very different ways. With rental units, the exemption is given to the owner of the building, not the tenant. For both affordable housing and market-rate tenants, these subsidies are received by the building while their units are subject to rent regulation. For condominium units, the exemption is directly received by the homeowner, which conceivably could alleviate the cost of homeownership for the duration of the exemption. However, it is also likely that the subsidy is captured by the developer or the reseller of a condo rather than the current homeowner, as the anticipated returns from the exemption could be built into the sale price of a condominium; this hypothesis is partially explored in the case study section herein.

Literature Review

Most previous research about the 421-a program took place around the time of its major reforms. A common claim at the time of the 2008 reforms was that the cost of development would be prohibitively high without 421-a. Multiple studies have cited that the majority of new construction was built without the program each year, so it was clearly possible to develop without the subsidy if needed (Cohen, 2008; Pratt Center for Community Development, 2005). A 2012 thesis at MIT and a 2014 study both conducted case studies of single buildings, one real and one fictional, using financial models to determine whether they would be considered feasible without 421-a. Both found that for the project in the chosen context, a 20% affordable housing component would not be financially feasible if there was no 421-a benefit (Brewer, 2015; Cohen, 2008; Wu, 2012). These studies support the current Mayor's proposal, supported by REBNY, in that maintaining 421-a for rental properties is likely to help support the development of more affordable housing which would not have otherwise been developed if 421-a is repealed outright.

Additional concepts were drawn from a research paper on property tax caps written in 2014, by Andrew Hayashi at the University of Virginia, School of Law. Hayashi found that on average, high-income neighborhoods were associated with the shortest tenures within their homes, where the properties that appreciate more rapidly are more likely to sell. Given that the intent of property tax caps is to help keep people in their homes despite an increase in property value, the regressive distribution and high turnover of its most-benefited properties indicates that the cap is not working as intended. Most importantly, he mentions that there is some evidence that the value of tax benefits could even be overcapitalized into the price of a home, allowing that benefit to be monetized by selling the property and perversely inducing owners to sell (Hayashi, 2014).

Most of the previous research on 421-a focused either on its broad effects and distribution, or in case studies, whether the feasibility of a project would be impacted by reform or expiration scenarios. While the feasibility of single projects forms the basis for studies of 421-a as a development subsidy, city policies cannot be judged on individual project feasibility by assuming all other factors will not change if the program is removed. Additionally, the direct beneficiaries of the program have not been sufficiently studied to see completely make these conditional arguments. The analysis for this Brief will use the latest datasets available to provide the broad scope of 421-a expenditure, and use the results to determine case study neighborhoods to study the effect at sale in one of its most heavily criticized applications which is also the focus of the pending previously referenced legislative deals: condominiums.

IV. FINDINGS

City-wide Analysis

When most people refer to the benefits granted by the 421-a exemption, they are referring to the 10, 15, 20, or 25 year exemption periods that begin after building construction. However, there are other two other significant factors that affect the exemption expenditure before the primary post-construction benefits are applied: assessed value caps, and construction period expenditure. The following are critical findings which stem from a city-wide analysis.

10% of the property tax base for these properties is already missing due to capped assessed values.

From the DOF data compiled data on the 2014 year, there was \$11,088,934,969 in effectively taxed assessed value for 421-a properties, while an additional \$1,164,037,173 in true assessed value was missing in the transitional assessed value numbers. Since taxes are based on the lower of either assessed or transitional value, this is just over 10% of the property tax base that is missing for these units, before the 421-a exemption is added as an additional bonus.

Construction period benefits additionally add significant exemption expenditure.

Additionally, construction period benefits are not subject to a phase-out schedule. An estimate of over \$1.6 billion in benefits was used to subsidize the construction period for the active 172,360 residential units receiving 421-a across the five boroughs. This averages out to just over \$9,000 in subsidies to construct each unit, before completion benefits began. When calculated by borough, this varies widely from an average of \$2,773 per unit in the Bronx, to \$15,963 in Manhattan.

Post-construction benefits are unevenly distributed across the boroughs: Manhattan's 39.4% of 421-a units make up 61% of all expenditure.

From a compiled study of the online 421-a spreadsheets provided on DOF's website, we find that Manhattan's 770 buildings only make up 6.7% of the total number of buildings receiving exemptions in the city, while the Bronx, Brooklyn, and Queens have thousands of buildings currently receiving the benefit. However, due to the far greater density of building in Manhattan, the borough also contains the highest total number of units: the 60,356 Manhattan units make up 39.4% of all active 421-a units in the city. This is an average of 78 units per address, compared to the citywide average of 13 units per address.

FIGURE 4: Comparison of the Number of 421-a Buildings vs. Units by Borough

Data from the Department of Finance 421-a website

FIGURE 5: 421-a Units and Expenditure by Borough, 2014

421-a units by borough in 2014

164,828 total units for active buildings
Data from DOF

421-a expenditure by borough in 2014

\$1,102,417,138 total estimated expenditure for active buildings
Data from IBO/MAS

At nearly \$670 million, Manhattan’s expenditure makes up 61% of the \$1.1 billion dollars in 2014 exemption benefits. Manhattan’s average expenditure per unit is \$11,062, which is 1.6x the citywide average of \$7,201 per unit and 4.2x the Bronx average of \$2,596. It is clear from this information that each large project awarded 421-a benefits has enormous consequences for the future expenditure of the program. On average, each Manhattan building collected \$870,000 benefits in 2014, and 5 buildings are collecting more than \$10 million annually each. The average 421-a expenditure for each unit in these buildings vary between \$12,000 to over \$18,000, compared with the Manhattan average of \$11,062.

Despite additional restrictions in the Geographic Exclusion Area (GEA), both the overall the expenditure and expenditure-per-unit within the GEA are greater than outside of it.

A total of 80,123 units fall within the exclusion area, making up 52% of total 421-a units. However, the expenditure-to-unit ratio for GEA units is much greater than for non-GEA units. With a cumulative expenditure of almost \$776 million, GEA units account for over 70% of 421-a expenditure for the year. In this case, the expenditure-to-unit ratio for an average GEA unit is 1.3x the average for all units, while non-GEA units have a ratio of 0.6x the average expenditure.

FIGURE 6: 421-a Units and Expenditure Within and Outside of the GEA

Data from IBO/MAS referenced against compiled GEA map

Data from IBO/MAS referenced against compiled GEA map

The lack of assessed value caps within the GEA has contributed to disproportionate expenditure in wealthier neighborhoods.

GEA caps only apply to as-of-right market-rate housing, and therefore the caps mostly did not apply to market-rate units within the GEA where 20% affordable housing was included. It was found that the number of units granted 421-a benefits both inside and outside of the GEA peaked in the base year of 2006, indicating a rush to take advantage of pre-reform exemptions and the impact of the recession. Only 405 of the 2,720 units with post-2008 base years are subject to exemption caps. This 15% cap rate for GEA properties is very low in comparison to the 74% cap rate for non-GEA properties which were granted benefits in the same period.

FIGURE 7: Number of Capped Units by GEA Inclusion Status and Base Year of Benefit

Data from DoF compilation for HDC compiled against GEA map

FIGURE 8: 421-a Expenditure by Location and Amount per Unit

TOTAL EXPENDITURE (2014 TAX YEAR)

- \$900 to \$5 million
- \$5 million to \$25 million
- \$25 million to \$50 million
- \$50 million to \$75 million
- \$75 million to \$90 million

EXPENDITURE PER UNIT (2014 TAX YEAR)

- up to \$3,000
- \$3,000 to \$6,000
- \$6,000 to \$10,000
- \$10,000+

Data compiled from:
 HPD's list of GEA properties
 DoF Tax Block maps (August 2014)
 MAS dataset from Independent Budget Office
 DoF 421-a online database

Referenced and edited against MAS GEA map

Mapping the expenditure by neighborhood shows that the greatest overall tax benefits are concentrated in Central Manhattan, with greater expenditure for uncapped GEA units. For the year 2014, based on an annual compounded cap amount of 3% and a tax rate of 12.855%, a capped unit is limited to receive a maximum of roughly \$9,977 in tax expenditure. This is an exemption on about \$172,474 in market value. Many neighborhoods within the GEA, and over 60% of Manhattan neighborhoods, are collecting an average expenditure per unit that is greater than this cap in a 100% benefit year, even though most of these units are well into their phase-out periods. The highest benefit awarded to a single uncapped unit with a post-2008 base year is a 20-year extended exemption for a 2013 condo located within a luxury tower development on the Upper East Side. With a market value of \$3.3 million and a full benefit value of \$1.4 million, its pre-phaseout expenditure is \$167,476, or almost 17x the expenditure cap that applies for most market-rate units outside of the GEA. An exemption cap on all market-rate units, regardless of GEA status, would have significantly decreased the cost of the program.

TABLE 3: Yearly Capped Unit Tax Expenditure and Market Value Equivalent
(based on 3% annual AV cap increase and historical Class 2 tax rates, rounded to nearest dollar)

Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
AV cap	\$65,000	\$66,950	\$68,959	\$71,027	\$73,158	\$75,353	\$77,613	\$79,942
Market value equivalent	\$144,444	\$148,778	\$153,241	\$157,838	\$162,573	\$167,451	\$172,474	\$177,648
Tax expenditure	\$8,356	\$8,606	\$8,865	\$9,131	\$9,404	\$9,687	\$9,977	\$10,277

Condominiums make up a disproportionately large part of 421-a expenditure.

One-third of the units receiving 421-a are condominiums. With 3/4 of New York City’s housing stock consisting of rental apartments and 69% of residents who rent rather than own, the units built with 421-a exemption favor condominium and other non-rental units compared to general city characteristics. Rentals, excluding condorentals, are 36% of the units that are collecting benefits but amount to only 28% of 421-a expenditure. On the other end of the spectrum, condominiums make up one-third of all units receiving 421-a exemption, but are nearly half of all current 421-a expenditure at \$537 million. Given this, the ratio of rental expenditure per unit is .8x the citywide average for all unit types, while the ratio of condominium expenditure per unit is 1.5x the average. This begs the question of the number of potential rental units which could be created if the subsidy from condominium units was shifted to deeper subsidies for the rental market.

Less than half of the units currently receiving 421-a are rental housing. Of the rental units, nearly 39,000, or 52%, are in rent-regulated buildings. This is consistent with existing city-wide rent-stabilization numbers, where approximately half of all rental units are subject to rent stabilization (Mayor’s Office of the City of New York, 2014) . Estimates on the exact number of affordable housing units subsidized through the program are not available. Estimates range from 9% from the Association for Neighborhood & Housing Development, to the 14% units affordable for up to 120% AMI reported in last year’s New School report (Association for Neighborhood and Housing Development, 2015; Coleman et al., 2014). It is unclear as to whether other these studies have tried to also assess condominium affordability, or whether such numbers only address the rental portion of 421-a expenditure.

FIGURE 9: 421-a Units and Expenditure by Building Type

421-a units by building category in 2014

164,828 total residential units represented
Data from Department of Finance

421-a spending by building category in 2014

\$1,102,417,138 total estimate, chart data rounded to nearest million
Expenditure data from IBO/MAS, matched to unit types from the Department of Finance

The neighborhoods of the Upper West Side between 59th and 79th Streets, and the Bronx neighborhood of Morrisania/Longwood were chosen as case study sites based on their 421-a expenditure and distribution of buildings receiving benefits.

Two neighborhoods were identified for additional study. As Manhattan’s expenditure per unit is the highest and the Bronx’s is the lowest, it was decided to choose one of the highest-expenditure neighborhoods from each borough. Although the Clinton neighborhood has a higher overall expenditure than the Upper West Side between 59th and 79th Streets, it was decided to study the UWS neighborhood because it had a greater proportion of expenditure going to condominiums than Clinton, which is consistent with most neighborhoods in Manhattan. Additionally, the Morrisania/Longwood neighborhood of the Bronx was selected as a case study. Although the Riverdale neighborhood has greater expenditure for condominiums, the Morrisania/Longwood neighborhood has the greatest amount of expenditure in the Bronx. Therefore, it was decided that it would be useful to show contrast in a neighborhood with more rental subsidy—therefore making for a more suitable comparative study. The average annual expenditure per unit in the Manhattan neighborhood is \$79,195, nearly 29x the \$2,749 expenditure per unit in the Bronx neighborhood. The Appendix contains an expenditure breakdown for all neighborhoods

FIGURE 10: Neighborhoods Chosen for Condominium Study

Manhattan: Upper West Side 59-79th Streets

Fiscal year 2014 total expenditure: \$79,828,966
 Number of residential units: 1,008
 Average annual expenditure per unit: \$79,195

EXPENDITURE BREAKDOWN

Bronx: Morrisania/Longwood

Fiscal year 2014 total expenditure: \$12,150,422
 Number of residential units: 4,419
 Average annual expenditure per unit: \$2,749

EXPENDITURE BREAKDOWN

*Data compiled from:
 HPD's list of GEA properties
 DoF Tax Block maps (August 2014)
 MAS dataset from Independent Budget Office
 DoF 421-a online database
 Referenced and edited against MAS GEA map*

Neighborhood Case Studies

Manhattan: Upper West Side (59-79th Streets)

3,175 sales of properties between January of 2003 and November of 2014 were selected that either are collecting 421-a exemptions., representing a total of 15 buildings. Of these, 2,544 total sales out of the total had data on all regression variables to be used. The variation in home prices was considerable, with the highest value fetching about 125x the price per square foot as the lowest sale. Most of the home prices were skewed toward the lower end of the spectrum, with a mean price per square foot of about \$1,667 and mean home value of \$2.95 million. The extreme variations in prices are reflected in a standard deviation of the sale amount that is greater than the mean value.

The regression results showed an adjusted R-squared of .32, meaning that the model is able to explain about 32% of the variation in price per square foot. The regression results have P values of 0.000 for all variables, which indicates that results are statistically significant. The effect of an estimated exemption left per square foot is positive, with a coefficient of 0.16 and .22 within a 95% confidence interval. The positive effect of the exemption is more impactful at this logarithmic scale than the effect of bedrooms, sale year, or year built of the unit. Square footage has already been accounted for both in sale price and the exemption remaining. While the natural log transformations are unable to provide a dollar-for-dollar increase on value for the exemption, this shows that the amount of 421-a exemption left at the time of sale is reflected in higher condominium sale prices.

TABLE 4: Manhattan Upper West Side (59-79th Streets) Applicable Sales Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Sale year	3175	2008.953	2.589599	2003	2014
Sale amount	3175	\$2,953,223.00	\$4,318,391.00	\$81,600.34	\$89,800,000.00
Price per square foot	3175	\$1,667.36	\$956.38	\$106.08	\$13,309.61
Bedrooms	3175	2.009449	1.029146	1	7
Year built	3175	1991.94	31.40928	1886	2009
Estimated exemption left at time of sale	2544	\$111,397.70	\$86,191.14	\$3,726.99	\$910,388.50
Estimated exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot	3175	\$56.02	\$34.90	\$0.00	\$195.16
ln (price per square foot)	3175	\$7.32	\$0.42	\$4.66	\$9.50
ln (Estimated exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot)	2544	\$4.16	\$0.47	\$1.55	\$5.27

TABLE 5: Manhattan Upper West Side (59-79th Streets) Estimated 421-a Remaining Regression Overview

Number of obs	F(4, 2539)	Prob > F	R-squared	Adj R-squared	Root MSE
2544	300.91	0	0.3216	0.3205	0.33316

TABLE 6: Manhattan Upper West Side (59-79th Streets) Estimated 421-a Remaining Regression Coefficients

ln (price per square foot [2015 dollars])	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	95% Conf. Interval	
Sale year	0.0406156	0.0033574	12.1	0.000	0.034032	0.0471992
Year built	-0.0959779	0.0051076	-18.79	0.000	-0.1059933	-0.0859625
Bedrooms	0.1315606	0.00695	18.93	0.000	0.1179324	0.1451889
ln (Estimated exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot)	0.1916617	0.0174287	11	0.000	0.1574859	0.2258375
_cons	117.3216	10.5954	11.07	0.000	96.54514	138.0981

Bronx: Morrisania/Longwood

This Bronx neighborhood saw a lot less development and condominium sales than the Upper West Side comparison. 65 unique addresses were found collecting 421-a data, although only 8 unique streets were represented: Boston Road, Brook Avenue, East 156th Street, East 158th Street, Franklin Avenue, Intervale Avenue, and St. Ann’s Avenue. 157 observations had the complete data required for regression, out of the 640 total transactions that took place during the study period. The home prices saw far less variation than in Manhattan, with a minimum price per square foot of just over \$100, to a maximum of \$534. The distribution of prices followed a fairly even bell curve, although a natural log transformation was still applied to home price per square foot and exemption remaining, in order to gain further linearity and to follow the same regression model as Manhattan.

The Morrisania/Longwood regression showed a higher adjusted R-squared value of .52 than the Upper West Side model. As there are many variables that were not able to be captured in this model, it is possible that more external

factors such as building amenities and proximity to the Hudson River or Central Park affect the home sale values in Manhattan than they do in this Bronx neighborhood. This models shows that the sale price of homes have lowered since 2003 rather than increased, as they have in the Upper West Side regression. The year built and number of bedrooms do not show a statistically significant correlation to the sale price, unlike the Manhattan results. This may be a result of a smaller sample size, as well as less difference between 1 and 3 bedrooms, rather than Manhattan's range of 1 to 7. It was not possible to run the regression again with only one bedroom size at a time, because the sample size was already fairly small.

The estimated exemption left per square foot also shows a statistically significant increase to the home value per square foot, with a $P > |t|$ of 0.009. The positive coefficient has a span of 0.036 to 0.244 over a 95% confidence interval. The coefficient for the exemption impact is larger than all other factors, except for the sale year. Again, it is clear from the model that the value of the exemption is reflected in the condominium sales price, and recognized by homeowners and developers upon the sale of the property.

TABLE 7: Bronx Morrisania/Longwood Applicable Sales Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Sale year	167	2009.078	1.261067	2007	2014
Sale amount	167	\$263,063.90	\$68,597.42	\$70,000.00	\$446,350.00
Price per square foot	167	\$298.20	\$74.16	\$100.50	\$533.93
Bedrooms	167	1.934132	0.5822446	1	3
Year built	167	2001.545	22.94748	1910	2009
Estimated exemption left at time of sale	157	\$103,315.20	\$32,698.77	\$50,220.38	\$279,742.50
Estimated exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot	167	\$108.97	\$40.93	\$0.00	\$208.87
In (price per square foot)	167	\$5.66	\$0.28	\$4.61	\$6.28
In (Estimated true exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot)	157	\$4.71	\$0.30	\$3.93	\$5.34

TABLE 8: Bronx Morissania/Longwood Estimated 421-a Remaining Regression Overview

Number of obs	F(4, 152)	Prob > F	R-squared	Adj R-squared	Root MSE
157	43.90	0.000	0.536	0.524	0.186

TABLE 9: Bronx Morissania/Longwood Estimated 421-a Remaining Regression Coefficients

In (price per square foot [2015 dollars])	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P > t	95% Conf. Interval	
Sale year	-0.1447095	0.0117306	-12.34	0.000	-0.1678855	-0.1215334
Year built	0.006042	0.0145721	0.41	0.679	-0.022748	0.034832
Bedrooms	0.0051806	0.026636	0.19	0.846	-0.047444	0.0578052
In (Estimated exemption left at time of sale per sq. foot)	0.1398646	0.0527275	2.65	0.009	0.0356911	0.244038
_cons	283.5942	38.09924	7.44	0.000	208.3218	358.8666

V. DISCUSSION

Below is a brief summary of the findings from both the city-wide data analysis and the neighborhood case studies:

- Over 10% of the original tax base is missing due to transitional assessed value caps before the 421-a is applied at all.
- Estimated pre-construction benefits average just over \$9,000 per unit city-wide, although it varies widely from Manhattan's \$15,963 to the Bronx's \$2,773.
- The expenditure-per-unit ratio was disproportionately high for condominiums at 1.5x the city average, the borough of Manhattan at 1.6x the city average, and within the GEA at 1.3x the city average.
- Significant expenditure is given through uncapped exemptions for market-rate units within the GEA.
- Exemption values are reflected in higher condominium sales prices, regardless of neighborhood and other factors in competitive markets which may drive up the cost of homes.

Although all findings have significant implications about the current performance and future of 421-a, it is useful to focus on the last two: uncapped market-rate exemptions within the GEA and higher condominium sale prices as a result of the exemption. It is commonly dismissed that all market-rate units are subject to an exemption cap, but market-rate units within the GEA are not, because they are not considered as-of-right developments. Given that these are the highest-valued properties in the city and placed in a zone that was intended to exclude granting excessive benefits to luxury housing, such market-rate units should be the primary target of assessed value exemption caps. The market-rate units in projects that include affordable housing are the largest beneficiaries of this exemption.

If 421-a is to continue within the GEA, it makes little sense for such uncapped exemptions on market-rate units to exist. As-of-right developments in depressed neighborhoods are not the subject of public outcry: luxury developments in the highest-priced neighborhoods of the city are. Since market-rate rentals built with 421-a are subject to rent regulation for the duration of their benefit period, a capped exemption for market-rate units could also contribute to affordability for higher earners. However, it makes little sense to grant unlimited benefits for some of the most luxurious apartments in the entire city.

In the evaluation of condominium sales, it was found that the sale price per square foot of a property was positively impacted for each dollar of exemption left on that property at time of sale, in both the Manhattan and Bronx neighborhood. This knowledge is intuitive, as a person who anticipates paying less in property taxes is willing to pay more for a home or to take out a larger mortgage. However, the implications of this finding can affect how one sees the role of post-construction exemptions for condominiums. By contrast, in a rental building, the post-construction exemption helps offset the cost of maintaining a building, and rent regulation is often applied for at least the duration of the exemption, allowing that money to fund the maintenance of rent-regulated apartments. This is a critical aspect for maintaining and preserving long-term affordability of units.

For condominiums, the post-construction exemption is captured by the seller. In most cases, there is no regulation on the price of condo sales. If a developer built an affordable unit condominium, which is relatively rare, there is also no check in place to ensure that the unit stays affordable after its first sale, for the duration of the exemption length. This has been a challenge to affordable housing policy nationwide as re-sale covenants have been enforced with ambiguous results. In this case, the first buyer would simply offer a higher bid for the unit to the condo developer, while the developer keeps that money with no commitment to housing affordability for the future of the condo. Each additional buyer is compensating for the cost of the exemption to the previous owner, and the exemption simply becomes a way to move wealth to the developer and early condominium owners. This phenomenon is not consistent with current public policy goals and is rightfully the target of the current pending legislative deal.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The debate on how to address 421-a when it comes up for renewal in June is crucial. In the highest-demand areas of the city, which the GEA attempts to encompass and where the vast majority of 421-a benefit is granted, there is arguably little justification to incentivize market-rate condominium development. Here, the goal of public policy should be for subsidizing rental housing which has some affordable component. The evidence of this Brief supports this proposition, as well as the pending legislative deal. Likewise, there is some basis to believe that an outright repeal of 421-a would be highly disruptive to the production of affordable rental housing.

Despite the tremendous growth in New York City, there are still areas of the city that see very little investment, such as many neighborhoods in the Bronx, which could benefit from tax incentives for market-rate rental units. Given that both the depressed and the high-demand inflated market conditions exist and that the program has spent an enormous amount of money to subsidize very little affordable housing relative to market-rate housing, it could be argued that the program should be discontinued in all but the most disinvested of neighborhoods. However, the larger goal is to produce rental housing both market-rate and affordable. Therefore, the pending legislative deal to require affordable housing in all developments benefiting from 421-a is likely to result in significant numbers of affordable units which would not have otherwise been developed.

From other literature reviewed, it is clear that the market is not likely to yield any affordable housing voluntarily without subsidy. However, the application of multiple subsidy programs for the same 20% means that the effect of each program is diminished, and the price of land will continue to be artificially inflated through expected tax breaks—particularly for condominium projects. However, while many economists believe that 421-a is priced into land prices, there is no solid empirical evidences to suggest that this is the case. This research projects ended its research with an example of two neighborhoods encompassing about 4,000 total sales transactions regardless of whether the condominiums would have qualified as affordable housing or not. That data is not publicly available. Although there are no restrictions in place for even an affordable condominium unit to prevent a first homebuyer from simply turning around and selling it to someone at a higher price, it is possible that there were some condominiums that qualified as affordable housing to the first homebuyer that were built under the program.

This Brief supports the pending legislative deal for the discontinuation of 421-a as applied to condominiums, but that does not mean that affordable homeownership in New York City is an invalid goal – it simply means that the 421-a program has not been an effective way of providing affordability for condominiums. Further research should also be conducted on affordable homeownership within the city to address alternatives. Likewise, further research is needed to see if off-site obligations for affordable units built in higher income neighborhoods make sense if they result in more aggregate units. The true cost of housing is just now being fully understood in terms of the dynamics between various neighborhoods in the city.

A reform of the 421-a program must set forth a clear statement of its intended goals, and it must develop a process which tirelessly tracks where all of the expenditures have gone so as to assess whether it is effectively and efficiently accommodating its own legislative intent. It is hoped that this research advances a dialogue which balances the interests of various public, civic and private stakeholders in promoting the production of housing. The pending legislative proposal of the Mayor's Office supported by REBNY reflects a strong statement as to the collective desire to promote the production of housing, as it speaks to the long-term viability of entire industries, neighborhoods and every day New Yorkers.

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APPENDIX

List of Acronyms

AMI	Area Median Income
ANHD	Association for Neighborhood and Housing Development
AV	Assessed Value
BBL	Borough-Block-Lot
DCP	Department of City Planning
DOF	Department of Finance
FMR	Fair Market Rent
HDC	Housing Development Corporation
HMFA	HUD Metro FMR Area
HPD	Housing Preservation and Development
HUD	Housing and Urban Development
GEA	Geographic Exclusion Area
IHP	Inclusionary Housing Program
LIHTC	Low-Income Housing Tax Credits
MAS	Municipal Art Society
MID	Mortgage Interest Deduction
NOI	Net Operating Income
ROE	Return on Equity

Data Sources

Area median income: <http://www.ffiec.gov/Medianincome.htm>

NYC Property database: <http://nycprop.nyc.gov/nycproperty/nynav/jsp/selectbbl.jsp>

Department of Finance property portal: <https://a836-propertyportal.nyc.gov/>

Property Shark: <http://www.propertyshark.com/mason/>

Additional Reference Tables

Accessed 3/20/2015 from the Bureau of Labor Statistics
http://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm

APPENDIX TABLE 1: Bureau of Labor Statistics Inflation Calculator

Year	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
2015 Value	\$1.27	\$1.24	\$1.20	\$1.16	\$1.13	\$1.09	\$1.09	\$1.07	\$1.04	\$1.02	\$1.00	\$0.99

Accessed 4/21 from the DOF tax exemption calculations
<https://a836-propertyportal.nyc.gov/calculations.aspx>

APPENDIX TABLE 2: 421-a Phase-Out Years with Percentage of Benefits

Year	10-year term	15-year term	20-year term	25-year term
1	100%	100%	100%	100%
2	100%	100%	100%	100%
3	80%	100%	100%	100%
4	80%	100%	100%	100%
5	60%	100%	100%	100%
6	60%	100%	100%	100%
7	40%	100%	100%	100%
8	40%	100%	100%	100%
9	20%	100%	100%	100%
10	20%	100%	100%	100%
11	Fully Taxable	100%	100%	100%
12	-	80%	100%	100%
13	-	60%	80%	100%
14	-	40%	80%	100%
15	-	20%	60%	100%
16	-	Fully Taxable	60%	100%
17	-	-	40%	100%
18	-	-	40%	100%
19	-	-	20%	100%
20	-	-	20%	100%
21	-	-	Fully Taxable	100%
22	-	-	-	80%
23	-	-	-	60%
24	-	-	-	40%
25	-	-	-	20%
26	-	-	-	Fully Taxable

MAS/IBO dataset merged with DOF data

APPENDIX TABLE 3: Expenditure by Neighborhood: Manhattan

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
CLINTON	\$33,872,518	\$15,858,228	\$11,329,270	\$18,128,625	\$7,669,671		\$86,858,311
UPPER WEST SIDE (59-79)	\$46,123,914	\$20,916,227		\$9,391,800		\$3,397,025	\$79,828,966
CHELSEA	\$25,167,781	\$18,236,978	\$4,094,481	\$850,753	\$6,139,883		\$54,489,876
HARLEM-CENTRAL	\$20,875,688	\$1,780,029	\$3,393,479	\$4,554,784	\$11,632,331	\$2,015,070	\$44,251,382
FASHION	\$6,670,724		\$13,817,778	\$23,598,357			\$44,086,859
MIDTOWN WEST	\$21,510,481	\$12,658,444	\$1,053,322	\$6,528,289	\$43,343		\$41,793,878
HARLEM-EAST	\$4,175,852	\$7,363,072	\$9,067,076	\$4,657,743	\$5,726,632	\$126,408	\$31,116,782
TRIBECA	\$16,011,103	\$3,785,760	\$3,186,423			\$92,135	\$23,075,421
UPPER EAST SIDE (79-96)	\$16,211,640	\$5,670,671					\$21,882,311
MURRAY HILL	\$12,321,149	\$3,075,129	\$5,963,329				\$21,359,607
FINANCIAL	\$7,073,440	\$6,243,079	\$7,388,514				\$20,705,033
JAVITS CENTER		\$14,965,983	\$4,930,573				\$19,896,556
FLATIRON	\$2,641,712	\$13,301,592			\$3,712,616		\$19,655,920
CIVIC CENTER	\$7,517,630	\$10,963,384					\$18,481,013
UPPER WEST SIDE (79-96)	\$3,454,027	\$4,219,497	\$574,252		\$437,788	\$3,516,548	\$12,202,111
SOUTHBRIDGE		\$256,295	\$355,270	\$490,635	\$11,016,360		\$12,118,560
UPPER WEST SIDE (96-116)	\$7,745,055	\$3,524,274			\$658,837		\$11,928,166
MIDTOWN CBD	\$11,909,890						\$11,909,890
UPPER EAST SIDE (59-79)	\$10,687,898	\$138,476	\$897,059			\$65,304	\$11,788,738
SOHO	\$10,759,095						\$10,759,095
GREENWICH VILLAGE-CENTRAL	\$3,461,475	\$93,687	\$106,466		\$2,140,490	\$3,169,628	\$8,971,746
KIPS BAY	\$8,110,485	\$574,798					\$8,685,284
EAST VILLAGE	\$2,664,672	\$1,186,318	\$487,156		\$413,103	\$3,567,769	\$8,319,019
MIDTOWN EAST	\$8,094,397	\$150,129					\$8,244,526
LOWER EAST SIDE	\$3,866,155	\$3,378,702	\$521,419		\$92,427	\$77,883	\$7,936,586
GREENWICH VILLAGE-WEST	\$6,777,464	\$821,358					\$7,598,823
ALPHABET CITY	\$1,406,177	\$714,187	\$752,595	\$928,566	\$1,313,121	\$169,571	\$5,284,217
MANHATTAN VALLEY	\$2,021,217		\$12,907	\$2,258,997	\$541,637	\$16,684	\$4,851,442
GRAMERCY	\$2,310,049		\$18,508				\$2,328,558
UPPER EAST SIDE (96-110)	\$2,171,685						\$2,171,685
CHINATOWN	\$1,737,051						\$1,737,051
LITTLE ITALY	\$424,640				\$1,010,289	\$76,284	\$1,511,213
HARLEM-UPPER	\$1,195,997					\$71,580	\$1,267,577
WASHINGTON HEIGHTS UPPER	\$984,138		\$49,286		\$96,799		\$1,130,223
INWOOD	\$312,867	\$122,020			\$185,911		\$620,798
HARLEM-WEST	\$555,313						\$555,313
WASHINGTON HEIGHTS LOWER	\$474,865						\$474,865

APPENDIX TABLE 4: Expenditure by Neighborhood: Bronx

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
MORRISANIA/LONGWOOD	\$963,101	\$3,068,640	\$2,877,916	\$2,649,253	\$2,440,387	\$151,126	\$12,150,422
HIGHBRIDGE/MORRIS HEIGHTS	\$90,879	\$2,669,637	\$369,774		\$606,181	\$46,144	\$3,782,616
RIVERDALE	\$1,885,350				\$556,094	\$196,584	\$2,638,028
MELROSE/CONCOURSE		\$1,614,074	\$78,632		\$701,985	\$12,092	\$2,406,784
KINGSBRIDGE/JEROME PARK	\$816,451	\$779,620	\$393,248		\$77,363		\$2,066,682
WILLIAMSBRIDGE	\$255,006				\$1,746,175	\$42,747	\$2,043,929
EAST TREMONT	\$161,775	\$729,928	\$221,098		\$626,409	\$246,431	\$1,985,641
SOUNDVIEW	\$1,053,168				\$863,496		\$1,916,664
BAYCHESTER	\$121,491	\$258,303	\$306,332		\$859,765	\$47,512	\$1,593,404
BEDFORD PARK/NORWOOD	\$164,361	\$629,180	\$401,893		\$327,466	\$61,426	\$1,584,326
BELMONT	\$158,393	\$219,371	\$72,396		\$897,903	\$34,416	\$1,382,479
WESTCHESTER		\$6,548	\$129,955		\$1,163,172	\$56,172	\$1,355,847
BRONXDALE			\$6,335		\$1,263,324		\$1,269,659
CROTONA PARK		\$312,606	\$134,827		\$514,357	\$196,686	\$1,158,477
MORRIS PARK/VAN NEST		\$233,356			\$915,665	\$5,874	\$1,154,896
FORDHAM		\$767,977	\$212,308		\$71,319		\$1,051,604
MOUNT HOPE/MOUNT EDEN		\$724,766	\$98,946		\$139,560		\$963,272
MOTT HAVEN/PORT MORRIS		\$93,951	\$377,577	\$52,919	\$337,623		\$862,070
SCHUYLerville/PELHAM BAY	\$311,673	\$5,885			\$294,511	\$49,669	\$661,738
COUNTRY CLUB	\$415,309				\$107,742		\$523,051
BATHGATE		\$185,183			\$217,852	\$15,687	\$418,723
THROGS NECK	\$143,166				\$100,612	\$26,857	\$270,635
CASTLE HILL/UNIONPORT	\$29,859				\$181,738	\$17,246	\$228,842
PARKCHESTER					\$223,315		\$223,315
PELHAM PARKWAY NORTH					\$218,607		\$218,607
FIELDSTON			\$5,190		\$185,138		\$190,329
KINGSBRIDGE HTS/UNIV HTS			\$6,596		\$180,539	\$637	\$187,771
WAKEFIELD					\$184,150		\$184,150
PELHAM PARKWAY SOUTH			\$22,356		\$62,610		\$84,967
CITY ISLAND	\$49,235						\$49,235
HUNTS POINT					\$43,352	\$5,557	\$48,909
WOODLAWN		\$6,797			\$21,263		\$28,060

APPENDIX TABLE 5: Expenditure by Neighborhood: Brooklyn

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
WILLIAMSBURG-NORTH	\$13,886,343		\$5,840,918	\$2,864,168	\$1,822,319	\$2,742,334	\$27,156,082
BEDFORD STUYVESANT	\$10,434,461	\$814,680	\$2,900,350	\$537,623	\$3,329,135	\$63,115	\$18,079,365
WILLIAMSBURG-EAST	\$7,723,824	\$1,257,491	\$2,459,746		\$5,599,474	\$446,566	\$17,487,101
WILLIAMSBURG-CENTRAL	\$11,595,755		\$472,754		\$323,816	\$1,544,196	\$13,936,522
WILLIAMSBURG-SOUTH	\$6,700,929		\$1,031,849	\$2,750,076	\$2,702,584	\$243,275	\$13,428,713
DOWNTOWN-METROTECH	\$7,143,937	\$5,316,002					\$12,459,939
GREENPOINT	\$5,354,673		\$1,429,659		\$1,976,460	\$256,979	\$9,017,771
DOWNTOWN-FULTON MALL	\$7,416,177	\$1,228,479			\$73,961		\$8,718,617
CROWN HEIGHTS	\$3,695,990	\$1,466,495	\$929,990		\$2,188,981	\$71,339	\$8,352,795
BOROUGH PARK	\$6,690,111		\$45,255	\$118,190	\$1,369,203	\$64,502	\$8,287,262
BRIGHTON BEACH	\$6,966,182		\$528,811		\$188,926	\$91,735	\$7,775,653
FORT GREENE	\$1,890,143	\$612,201	\$2,128,147		\$2,068,993	\$135,010	\$6,834,494
BOERUM HILL	\$5,355,016	\$467,928	\$523,324		\$154,446		\$6,500,713
PARK SLOPE	\$5,154,484		\$621,390		\$321,294	\$17,675	\$6,114,843
SUNSET PARK	\$4,719,214	\$220,672			\$835,287	\$70,671	\$5,845,844
DOWNTOWN-FULTON FERRY	\$5,031,408	\$162,897	\$599,219				\$5,793,524
GRAVESEND	\$4,641,359		\$32,006		\$642,674	\$119,279	\$5,435,317
SHEEPSHEAD BAY	\$4,198,774		\$739,276		\$382,345	\$77,409	\$5,397,804
PARK SLOPE SOUTH	\$2,933,361	\$506,929	\$920,077		\$118,687		\$4,479,055
BUSHWICK	\$407,284	\$347,008	\$656,450	\$131,435	\$2,592,185	\$342,874	\$4,477,237
CLINTON HILL	\$2,437,592	\$374,115	\$891,589		\$442,278	\$185,905	\$4,331,480
GOWANUS	\$2,141,836		\$1,039,791		\$517,527	\$36,966	\$3,736,120
MADISON	\$2,033,257		\$542,498		\$68,486	\$247,786	\$2,892,027
OCEAN PARKWAY-NORTH	\$1,317,072		\$873,631		\$305,838	\$358,462	\$2,855,003
BAY RIDGE	\$1,889,274	\$51,266	\$91,591		\$403,625	\$361,085	\$2,796,841
CARROLL GARDENS	\$1,963,732		\$432,244	\$136,574	\$138,092		\$2,670,641
BENSONHURST	\$2,020,616		\$3,339		\$526,421		\$2,550,377
MIDWOOD	\$1,936,674		\$9,745		\$325,811	\$96,375	\$2,368,605
FLATBUSH-NORTH	\$1,578,556		\$412,957		\$156,016		\$2,147,529
PROSPECT HEIGHTS	\$1,904,845				\$93,201	\$40,076	\$2,038,123
COBBLE HILL-WEST	\$1,340,263				\$457,173	\$113,549	\$1,910,984
BATH BEACH	\$1,468,729				\$388,403	\$22,842	\$1,879,974
FLATBUSH-CENTRAL	\$1,412,848		\$11,160		\$364,943		\$1,788,951
BROOKLYN HEIGHTS	\$1,645,773						\$1,645,773
EAST NEW YORK	\$281,991	\$699,343	\$278,310		\$361,711	\$9,828	\$1,631,183
BERGEN BEACH	\$901,484	\$542,842					\$1,444,326
OCEAN PARKWAY-SOUTH	\$965,426		\$126,290		\$160,718	\$94,553	\$1,346,987
WYCKOFF HEIGHTS	\$663,882				\$596,055		\$1,259,937
WINDSOR TERRACE	\$800,959		\$128,769		\$264,795		\$1,194,522

CONT. APPENDIX TABLE 5: *Expenditure by Neighborhood: Brooklyn*

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
MILL BASIN	\$73,934				\$1,026,080		\$1,100,014
DYKER HEIGHTS	\$846,145				\$97,523		\$943,668
KENSINGTON	\$768,640				\$156,474		\$925,114
CANARSIE	\$718,405				\$96,197		\$814,602
FLATBUSH-LEFFERTS GARDEN	\$662,042		\$56,798		\$47,548		\$766,388
CONEY ISLAND	\$220,693	\$149,724			\$32,173	\$57,609	\$460,200
RED HOOK	\$89,175		\$232,705		\$117,983		\$439,863
FLATBUSH-EAST	\$280,199	\$1,051			\$156,285	\$2,184	\$439,718
OCEAN HILL			\$216,500		\$173,052	\$8,120	\$397,672
BUSH TERMINAL	\$41,881		\$193,885		\$16,046	\$66,397	\$318,210
COBBLE HILL	\$310,417						\$310,417
MARINE PARK	\$196,982					\$4,738	\$201,719
FLATLANDS						\$108,841	\$108,841
BROWNSVILLE		\$12,875			\$88,730		\$101,605
MANHATTAN BEACH	\$101,348						\$101,348
CYPRESS HILLS					\$82,980		\$82,980
NAVY YARD	\$40,157						\$40,157
OLD MILL BASIN	\$6,076						\$6,076
GERRITSEN BEACH	\$4,044						\$4,044

APPENDIX TABLE 6: Expenditure by Neighborhood: Queens

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
FLUSHING-NORTH	\$19,883,168	\$1,843,566	\$687,409		\$4,428,387	\$517,128	\$27,359,657
ASTORIA	\$5,951,065	\$3,864,355	\$3,036,146	\$971,795	\$6,765,212	\$785,038	\$21,373,610
CORONA	\$3,648,213	\$985,375	\$242,237		\$11,618,965	\$415,708	\$16,910,498
LONG ISLAND CITY	\$11,123,576	\$517,534	\$2,970,466		\$885,464	\$117,654	\$15,614,695
ELMHURST	\$3,785,677	\$319,091	\$203,608	\$43,860	\$4,882,119	\$97,584	\$9,331,938
JAMAICA	\$1,902,198	\$352,442	\$1,489,972	\$136,545	\$2,844,950	\$533,112	\$7,259,219
FLUSHING-SOUTH	\$1,132,841	\$805,744	\$1,964,370		\$414,405	\$1,019,839	\$5,337,199
WOODSIDE	\$2,684,704	\$657,790	\$65,574		\$1,650,107	\$127,292	\$5,185,466
BRIARWOOD	\$1,010,139	\$254,103	\$2,242,864		\$1,180,941	\$52,780	\$4,740,828
REGO PARK	\$1,144,778	\$1,273,553	\$251,642		\$168,106	\$733,089	\$3,571,167
KEW GARDENS	\$1,759,187	\$113,938	\$914,725		\$715,388		\$3,503,238
FOREST HILLS	\$1,992,377		\$107,940		\$989,573	\$101,678	\$3,191,569
FAR ROCKAWAY	\$1,168,376	\$346,544			\$679,215		\$2,194,135
JACKSON HEIGHTS	\$608,692		\$102,564		\$990,972	\$17,126	\$1,719,353
HAMMELS	\$874,235		\$355,086		\$236,687	\$8,693	\$1,474,702
MIDDLE VILLAGE	\$675,610				\$517,150		\$1,192,760
ROCKAWAY PARK	\$1,000,847				\$60,126	\$42,279	\$1,103,251
RIDGEWOOD	\$766,352				\$222,450	\$10,137	\$998,939
COLLEGE POINT	\$457,464				\$228,540	\$59,431	\$745,436
RICHMOND HILL	\$4,323		\$123,803	\$51,762	\$504,014	\$32,325	\$716,227
SUNNYSIDE	\$523,011	\$75,326	\$41,162		\$20,486		\$659,986
OZONE PARK	\$184,901				\$288,952		\$473,853
JAMAICA ESTATES	\$211,834				\$214,881	\$8,449	\$435,164
BAYSIDE	\$149,986				\$273,987		\$423,974
SPRINGFIELD GARDENS		\$217,946	\$94,933		\$98,170		\$411,049
GLENDALE	\$52,012				\$298,860	\$32,896	\$383,768
MASPETH	\$141,826				\$203,182	\$28,047	\$373,055
EAST ELMHURST		\$4,331			\$365,284		\$369,616
ARVERNE		\$96,980			\$211,762	\$21,400	\$330,141
HOLLIS	\$123,174		\$5,441		\$117,155		\$245,770
LITTLE NECK					\$242,066		\$242,066
WOODHAVEN			\$2,609		\$190,598		\$193,207
ROSEDALE			\$29,941		\$159,296		\$189,238
BEECHHURST	\$184,170						\$184,170
HOWARD BEACH					\$154,517		\$154,517
JAMAICA HILLS					\$130,467		\$130,467
DOUGLASTON	\$75,806				\$5,830		\$81,635
HILLCREST					\$67,723		\$67,723
QUEENS VILLAGE					\$49,016		\$49,016

CONT. APPENDIX TABLE 6: *Expenditure by Neighborhood: Queens*

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
FRESH MEADOWS	\$44,447						\$44,447
SOUTH JAMAICA	\$17,003				\$24,842		\$41,845
FLUSHING MEADOW PARK					\$37,476		\$37,476
SO. JAMAICA-BAISLEY PARK					\$36,694		\$36,694
OAKLAND GARDENS					\$15,980		\$15,980
CAMBRIA HEIGHTS					\$4,819		\$4,819
SOUTH OZONE PARK					\$956		\$956

APPENDIX TABLE 7: *Expenditure by Neighborhood: Staten Island*

	CONDOS	RENTALS – REG.	RENTALS – UNREG.	RENTALS - OTHER	OTHER	-	Grand Total
NEW BRIGHTON-ST. GEORGE	\$546,845						\$546,845
GRYMES HILL	\$34,855				\$489,285		\$524,141
STAPLETON		\$16,173	\$2,353		\$442,392		\$460,918
CONCORD-FOX HILLS	\$35,738				\$335,424		\$371,162
STAPLETON-CLIFTON	\$198,082						\$198,082
NEW BRIGHTON		\$3,921	\$148,173		\$35,801		\$187,894
MARINERS HARBOR		\$104,758	\$13,415		\$52,894		\$171,067
MIDLAND BEACH					\$135,015		\$135,015
GREAT KILLS	\$110,474						\$110,474
PORT RICHMOND	\$46,474	\$3,181			\$3,342	\$43,918	\$96,915
NEW DORP	\$73,274						\$73,274
TOTTENVILLE	\$13,784				\$51,550		\$65,333
ELTINGVILLE	\$49,738						\$49,738
NEW DORP-HEIGHTS	\$47,668						\$47,668
ROSEBANK					\$45,013		\$45,013
CONCORD	\$35,880						\$35,880

Accessed 4/17/2015 from the Department of Finance
(<http://www1.nyc.gov/site/finance/taxes/property-tax-rates.page>)

APPENDIX TABLE 8: *Property Tax Rates for NYC Tax Classes*

YEAR	CLASS 1	CLASS 2	CLASS 3	CLASS 4
2014-2015	19.157%	12.855%	11.125%	10.684%
2013-2014	19.191%	13.145%	11.902%	10.323%
2012-2013	18.569%	13.181%	12.477%	10.288%
2011-2012	18.205%	13.433%	12.473%	10.152%
2010-2011	17.364%	13.353%	12.631%	10.312%
2009-2010	17.088%	13.241%	12.743%	10.426%

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